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Effectiveness of Japanese Animated Series with English Subtitles on the Vocabulary and Reading Comprehension Skills of High School Students

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Abstract

Aim: This study determined the effectiveness of Japanese Animated Series with English subtitles on the vocabulary and reading comprehension skills of high school students.

Methodology: This study was conducted at Malimono District, Malimono, Surigao del Norte with 81 respondents. Mean and Percentage Count was used to obtain the sample size of the respondents. In gathering data, the researcher-made questionnaire utilized a causal-comparative design of a research. There were 81 respondents to whom the questionnaire were floated.

Results: Results of the study showed that as to sex, the majority of the respondents are male. Most of the learners belong to the low-income family. As to the status of watching anime series most of the respondents have a high exposure to Japanese anime series with English subtitles.

Conclusion: There is significant difference wherein students who have exposure to Japanese animated films with English subtitles performed better in vocabulary and reading comprehension as compared to those who did not.

Keywords: *comprehension, causal-comparative, Japanese Animated Series, Subtitles*

INTRODUCTION

Animation provides a means of visual storytelling and entertainment that can provide enjoyment and information to people of all ages everywhere (Disney, 2017)

In the realm of language acquisition, popular culture in Japanese animation is becoming more popular. Some scholars have examined the positive impacts of animation on boosting learners' language skills. The name "anime" refers to any animated series generated by Japanese studios, which account for about 60% of all anime television programming worldwide (Napier & Susan, 2016). All of this emphasizes the value of animated videos for conveying both visual and audio information. The right side of the brain, which is responsible for art and data analysis, is responsible for processing visual information. Auditory information, on the other hand, is evaluated by the left hemisphere of the brain, which is responsible for analytic and interpretative calculations (Munir, 2016).

Traditional learning aids, on the other hand, heavily stimulate the left hemisphere of the brain, making learning tedious and monotonous (Armour & Iida, 2016).

Many people in today's generation enjoy watching Japanese anime programs with English subtitles. The majority of them are students who are passionate about it. They choose to watch anime shows that will entertain them rather than read books. Reading books causes kids to become easily bored since they come across words that they are unfamiliar with (Alferez, et al., 2023; Amihan & Sanchez, 2023; Dizon & Sanchez, 2020; Salendab & Dapitan, 2021a).

The field of foreign/second language instruction has improved significantly in recent years as a result of rapid advances in science, technology, and media, particularly in terms of the function of language classes (Muñoz & Sanchez, 2023; Salendab, 2021; Salendab & Dapitan, 2020; Sanchez, 2022). The use of technical gadgets in the classroom, such as a television, an LCD projector, a laptop, a DVD player, and video materials, has improved the

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quality of language instruction (Cakir 2018; Carvajal & Sanchez, 2023; Salendab, 2023; Salendab & Akmad, 2023; Sanchez, 2023a; Sanchez & Sarmiento, 2020).

However, according to Badir (2019), students struggle with vocabulary and reading comprehension. Students face such a terrible issue. According to Nabeel (2017), the announcement of a reading assignment in certain English classes causes students to complain because they anticipate the time commitment and the time-consuming effort of seeking up word definitions in dictionaries. Worse, students are unable to comprehend the content following such a tedious exercise.

Learners can improve their vocabulary and reading comprehension skills by watching anime films with subtitles. Because they are quick to read a variety of texts, students who enjoy reading will eventually extend their vocabulary size and have the capacity to determine word meanings, as opposed to poor and reluctant readers who are less likely to expand their vocabulary knowledge through wide reading. (Gunobgunob, 2019).

According to Corpuz (2020), the use of subtitled anime films helps students improve not only their vocabulary but also their pronunciation and reading comprehension. Students who enjoy reading will eventually expand their vocabulary and ability to determine the meaning of words, as they can quickly read different materials, compared to poor and reluctant readers who are less likely to expand their vocabulary skills through a broad reading.

In the modern age of education, students increasingly demand engaging, customized multimedia content (Salendab & Cogo, 2022; Salendab & Dapitan, 2021b; Salendab & Sanchez, 2023; Sanchez, 2023b). Animation constitutes a powerful pedagogical tool by combining audio messages with tailored visual cues and graphics, to serve the dual functions of explaining complex concepts and engaging student interest in the learning process.

This study explored the effect of the use of Japanese animated videos with English subtitles to augment the vocabulary and reading comprehension of junior high school students.

Many researchers have presented strong evidence that multimedia have useful effects on language learning because of rich and authentic comprehensible input. Subtitled animation cartoon is one of the best examples.

Gorjian (2014) defines subtitling as an audiovisual branch language in which the viewer can see statements in discussions on the screen while simultaneously observing images and listening to the talks.

Hidayat (2016) claimed that subtitled can provide learners with access to the authentic text of a native speaker, expose them to the target language, and allow them to utilize it in daily activities, even if they are unable to communicate with the native speaker due to limited access.

Besides, Sabouri and Zohrabi (2015) expressed that there have been such countless fruitful examinations on the many advantages and uses of captions and subtitles on record and TV that the requirement for captions and subtitling has been perceived, and significant regulations have been passed commanding its accessibility.

Subtitles in audiovisuals can facilitate other aspects of second language learning such as vocabulary acquisition, or overall plot comprehension. Also, the learners paid some attention when subtitles are presented (Long, 2010).

According to Gunderson, Odo, and D'Silva (2011), same language subtitling (SLS) has been a success in rural India. It has helped provide literacy, also for L2 literacy (L2L), and has promoted reading through a simple and effective method for language development. This report is from an area that is not as literal as urban areas, but it is still interesting to note as language learning is an important issue at all levels of society. Danan (2004) still claims that captions can be valuable for comprehension, word recognition, and vocabulary building.

Theories of Vocabulary

Vocabulary is a collection of English words with various meanings and functions that allow people to refer to objects and form logical statements. It is regarded as the cornerstone of English proficiency, thus learners must emphasize its acquisition as a vital part of language learning.

Ridarman (2017), defines the vocabulary that the experts have formulated from their unique perspectives before delving into the vocabulary. These are some of the many suggested vocabulary definitions. According to Hatch and Brown (1995 cited by Ridarman, 2017), the term vocabulary refers to a list or set of words for a particular language or a list of words used by individual speakers of the language. Since vocabulary is a list, the only system involved is alphabetical order. The choice of vocabulary selection and the methods used in vocabulary learning are important factors. Thus, the learning process in context is necessary to understand the meaning of words.

Vocabulary is fundamental to the language and vital to the typical language learner. Furthermore, he added that vocabulary is fundamental for the typical language learner and makes vocabulary a basic building block for mastering the four language skills of listening, speaking, reading, and writing. Without enough vocabulary, a language learner will not master language skills.

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Vocabulary is divided into two types, namely receptive vocabulary, and productive vocabulary. Receptive vocabulary is words that students recognize and understand when they occur in context, but cannot be produced correctly. It is a vocabulary that students recognize when they see it in the context of reading, but they don't use it when they speak and write.

While productive vocabulary is the words that students can understand, pronounce correctly, and use constructively while speaking and writing. It includes what is needed for receptive vocabulary, as well as the ability to speak or write the appropriate amount of time.

Teaching English Vocabulary

The teaching of vocabulary is not easy to do because people predominantly feel tired of the unlimited number of vocabulary. To some, vocabulary teaching even appears to be a waste of time. Whereas, as previously argued, vocabulary mastery is the pathway to mastering four paramount skills in English. Vocabulary is a central of English language acquisition, as suggested by Celce and Murcia (2001) in which vocabulary learning is central to language acquisition whether the language is first, second, or foreign. Furthermore, vocabulary mastery is an important thing to mastering four major skills such as speaking, reading, writing, and listening. For that reason, it is important to know principles in teaching vocabulary (Salendab & Laguda, 2023; Sanchez, 2020; Sanchez, Sanchez & Sanchez, 2023).

Vocabulary Skill

Vocabulary is essential to reading comprehension and plays an important part in the reading process (Sanchez, et al., 2022). The majority of words are learned indirectly by children through their daily interactions with speech and written language. Other terms are picked up through attentive instruction. The words we need to know to communicate successfully are referred to as vocabulary. Listening, speaking, reading, and writing are four sorts of language that educators commonly consider.

Vocabulary plays an important part in learning to read. Beginning readers must use the words they hear orally to make sense of the words they see in print. Kids who hear more words spoken at home learn more words and enter school with a better vocabulary. This larger vocabulary pays off exponentially as a child progresses through school.

Reading Comprehension as a Skill

Reading comprehension is one of the four English skills to be mastered by its learners. It is regarded as a vital component to reaching the goal of the teaching-learning process.

Reading is an activity involving constant guesses that are rejected and confirmed. It means that the readers need to comprehend what they are reading to get the idea of the passage.

Comprehension cannot be separated while doing a reading. Cowell (2012) in his research affirms that comprehension in reading is a process in which the reader constructs meaning while, or after, interacting with a text through the combination of prior knowledge and prior experience, information in text, the stance he or she takes concerning the text, and immediate, remembered, or anticipated social interactions and communications.

The National Reading Panel report focuses on text and the reader as a source of variability, in analyses by a variety of colleagues (Elliot, 2017) have identified comprehension as requiring the reader to take charge of the text, task, and context variables, presumably an implicit acknowledgment that text, task, and context are all important in defining reading comprehension and can be obstacles to comprehension, while at the same time the reader is seen as the most central element.

Teaching Reading

Reading is a receptive language process. It is the process of recognition, interpretation, and perception of written or printed materials. Reading proficiency plays a great role in understanding a written statement accurately and efficiently. Reading serves as an important tool in every field of professional service.

The current research based view of reading is that it is an interactive process, involving knowledge of the world and various types of language knowledge, any of which may interact with any other to contribute to text comprehension (Khan, 2007).

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Research Questions

This study aimed to assess the extent of the vocabulary and reading comprehension performances of the Junior High School students in the Malimono District as effect of their exposure to animated Japanese animated series with English subtitles.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following sub-problems:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of the following aspects;
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 sex;
 - 1.3 monthly income of parents; and
 - 1.4 degree of exposure to Japanese animated films with English subtitles?
2. What is the extent of performances among the respondents in terms of the following;
 - 2.1 Vocabulary
 - 2.2 Reading comprehension?
3. Do the age, sex, and family monthly income of the students significantly relate to their vocabulary and reading performances?
4. Is there any significant difference in the vocabulary and reading performances of students between those who are exposed to Japanese animated films with English subtitles and those without exposure?

Hypothesis

Given the stated research problem, the following hypotheses were tested on 0.05 level of significance:

Hypothesis 1: The age, sex, and family monthly income of the students do not significantly relate to their vocabulary and reading performances.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the vocabulary and reading performances of students who are exposed to Japanese animated films with English subtitles and those without exposure when grouped according to the aspects as cited in Problem 4.

METHODS

Research Design

This study utilized a causal-comparative research design for it examined potential causes for observed differences found among existing groups. For this study, the researcher likely focused on comparing the grade 11 students' vocabulary and reading comprehension performances between those who are exposed to the Japanese animated movie with English subtitles and those without exposure to such.

Population and Sampling

The study was conducted among the selected secondary schools under the Malimono District namely; Malimono National High School, Bunyasan National School, Masgad National High School, and Cantapoy National High School.

Instrument

In this study, the researcher utilized a researcher-made questionnaire as its research instrument. This researcher-made questionnaire was composed of two parts; Part 1 determined the demographic profile of the respondents and Part 2 was the experts' validated twenty items (20) multiple-choice test to measure the vocabulary and reading comprehension of the respondents.

Moreover, printed literary pieces one from the following genres; essay, poem, and short story were also made available as springboard material to determine the extent of the vocabulary and reading performance of those students that have exposure to Japanese anime movies with English language subtitles and those without exposure.

These research instruments were exposed to validity and reliability test to ensure that these measures what it was designed to measure.

Validity. The instrument's content was subjected to validation by presenting its draft to the panel of examiners and professionals who were regarded as experts in the field. After coming up with their valuable comments and suggestions on the refinement of the instrument. The researcher had carried out integrating such in the revision and in final crafting of the questionnaire ready for its routing.

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Reliability. A trial run of the research instrument was administered to the non-respondents of the study in order to test the reliability of such. The result in the conduct of run-rerun was said to be reliable. Hence, gave a scientific signal that such is worthy to be administered to the target respondents. The process was immediately instituted after the researcher was done with the content validation.

Data Collection

The researcher has undergone the following procedures in gathering the prescribed data vital for the study;

The researcher first sent request letters addressed to the Dean of the Graduate School and to the Department of Education (DepEd) Division Schools Superintendent, of Surigao del Norte to ask permission to administer the research instrument to the target respondents.

After obtaining the said permit from them, another letter of approval was then again sent to the School Principals or School Heads for the researcher to be allowed to conduct the study to the target respondents in their respective National High Schools.

Once the approval from the aforementioned people was sought, the researcher immediately proceeded to the targeted research locale and respondents.

As preliminaries prior to data gathering proper, the researcher had to segregate or classify the number of grade 11 students per school as to whether they have exposure to Japanese anime movies with English subtitles or no exposure at all.

Immediately, after accurate data were gathered as to those students with exposure and no exposure to Japanese anime movies with English subtitles, the printed literary pieces on the genre of essay, poem, and short story were given to the respondents.

One literary piece per session or day was read by the respondents in the span of twenty (20) minutes. After the given moment for reading was consumed, the twenty (20) items vocabulary and reading comprehension test was administered to the respondents. They were given another twenty (20) minutes to answer such.

After doing so, retrieval of the questionnaires then followed. The data was then kept for proper consolidation, tabulation, and statistical treatment.

Treatment of Data

The following statistical tools were used in treating the data of the study;

Frequency Count and Percentage Count. These tools were used to determine the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of sex and status of watching anime series. Frequency count and percentage were appropriate data analysis tools to be used when the data are in nominal or categorical scale such as sex with male and female categories and status of watching anime series with 'yes' and 'no' categories.

Mean and Standard Deviation. These tools were used to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of age and income. These were also used to determine the extent of the vocabulary and pronunciation performance of the respondents. These were appropriate data analysis tools to describe interval and ratio scales or quantitative data such as age, income, and extent of vocabulary and pronunciation performance of the students which are actual quantities.

Point Biserial Correlation. This was used to determine the relationship between sex and the performances of the respondents. This is an appropriate tool in determining the degree of relationship between a nominal data with two natural categories such as sex having male and female categories and data in interval/ratio scales such as performances of the respondents.

Pearson-r. This was used to determine if age and income significantly relate to the performances of the respondents in terms of vocabulary and reading comprehension. This is an appropriate tool in determining the degree of relationship between sets of data in interval/ratio scales such as performances of the respondents and their profile in terms of age and income.

One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). This was used to compare the performances between respondents who watch and those who don't watch Japanese anime series. This tool is used to compare quantitative values such as performance in vocabulary and reading comprehension between two or more groups or categories such as status of watching Japanese anime series with two groups: those who watch Japanese anime series and those who don't.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher ensured that all research protocols involving ethics in research were complied with for the protection of all people and institutions involved in the conduct of the study.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 below presents the profile of the respondents and the result in the test of significant difference between the demographic profile and the impact of watching Japanese animated series with English subtitles.

Table 1. Profile of Students

Profile		f(n=81)	Percent
Sex	Male	44	54.3
	Female	37	45.7
Status of watching anime series	Yes	48	59.3
	No	33	40.7
		Mean	SD
Age		17.31	2.28
Income		5742.11	4003.15

Based on the table above, it can be gleaned that *as to sex, majority of the total number of respondents are male (44 or 54.3%)* female was only (37 or 45.7%a).

In terms of age, the sum of the average computed was 17.31 and its dispersion of data is 2.28. Such showed a normal distribution.

Looking into its income, data revealed that the *average of the computed monthly income was 5742.11* while its distribution is 4003.15. With this scenario it just showed that parents of the respondents was categorized as poor income earner per released classification of social class by the Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS).

As to the *status of watching anime series*, it can be viewed from the table that *majority of the respondents (48 or 59.3%)* have exposure to Japanese anime series with English subtitles, while 33 or 45.7% of the respondents claimed that they have no exposure to such. This correlates to the idea of Kincaid (2020) which emphasized that anime has now become the favorite entertainment material for children and teenagers from all over the world, including our country. This is because of the glory of its characters, such as Naruto, Goku, Doraemon, Sin Chan and many others, coupled with the aesthetic presentation of the graphics illustrated that makes the anime very attractive. Similarly, the study of Denson (2018) had revealed the teens do have a great liking for and fondness on anime. This is because it is fun, interesting, realistic, and humorous.

Extent as to the Vocabulary Performance of the Respondents

Table 2 below displays the extent as to the vocabulary performance of the respondents.

Table 2. Vocabulary Performance of the Respondents

Watching Anime Series	Genre	Mean	SD	Percent Score	Transmuted Score	Description
Yes	Essay	8.69	1.29	86.88	91	Outstanding
	Poem	7.96	1.46	79.58	87	Very Satisfactory
	Short Story	8.71	1.24	87.08	92	Outstanding
	Total	25.35	2.94	84.51	90	Outstanding
No	Essay	8.36	1.37	83.64	89	Very Satisfactory
	Poem	7.15	1.60	71.52	82	Satisfactory
	Short Story	8.00	2.17	80.00	87	Very Satisfactory

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Total 23.52 4.25 78.38 86 Very Satisfactory

Legend:

Scale	Qualitative Description	Verbal Interpretation (VI)
90 - 100	Outstanding	Very Proficient
85 - 89	Very Satisfactory	Proficient
80 - 84	Satisfactory	Moderately Proficient
75 - 79	Fairly Satisfactory	Less Proficient
Below 75	Did Not Meet Expectation	Poor

It can be gleaned from the table above that as to vocabulary performance, the students with exposure to Japanese anime series with English subtitles were perceived to be **generally outstanding or very proficient (M=25.35)**. This likely means that the students have a great vocabulary knowledge and experience and that this further implies that they possessed a thorough competence derived from training and practice. Hence, students can independently apply this knowledge through authentic performance assignments.

Meanwhile, the students with no exposure to anime series with English subtitles were **very satisfactory or proficient** as described by the overall mean assessment of 23.52.

With these, it can be deduced that there is no statistical difference between the group who watched or have exposure to Japanese anime series with English subtitles (Yes) as compared with the group who does not watch or have no exposure to Japanese anime series with English subtitles (No).

In this case, the null hypothesis is accepted, signifying that the respondents who watch and do not watch Japanese anime series with English subtitles play a significant role in improving instruction.

Results indicated above are similar to the findings presented in Zanon (2016) study wherein it was concluded that subtitled content was more effective in facilitating language learning compared to dubbed content because more senses are utilized: subtitled content utilizes audio, visual, and textual information whereas dubbed content only has two, audio and visual.

Moreover, watching anime is not only limited to acquiring vocabulary. It can also facilitate new learning in terms of diversity such as countries' culture, traditions, practices, and beliefs whether it is subtitled or dubbed anime as long as it is shown in the film through the characters' gestures and setting and story's plot and its universal message which is the theme.

Gorjian (2017) claimed that anime increases students' motivation to learn. It definitely enriches classes, stimulates discussion and increases students' ability to acquire new vocabularies and aid the difficulties of language. Hence, such is an important educational medium in the language classrooms, which enlivens and enriches students' interest to achieve the goal of teaching and learning the second language.

Reading Comprehension Performance of the Respondents

As to the reading comprehension performance of the respondents, Table 3 presents it in detail.

Table 3. Reading Comprehension Performance of the Respondents

Watching Anime Series	Genre	Mean	SD	Percent Score	Transmuted Score	Description
Yes	Essay	9.27	1.07	92.71	95	Outstanding
	Poem	7.83	1.58	78.33	86	Very Satisfactory
	Short Story	8.79	1.03	87.92	92	Outstanding
	Total	25.90	2.44	86.32	91	Outstanding
No	Essay	9.30	1.45	93.03	95	Outstanding

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Poem	6.55	2.15	65.45	78	Fairly Satisfactory
Short Story	8.27	1.59	82.73	89	Very Satisfactory
Total	24.12	3.30	80.40	87	Very Satisfactory

Legend:

Scale	Qualitative Description	Verbal Interpretation (VI)
90 - 100	Outstanding	Very Proficient
85 - 89	Very Satisfactory	Proficient
80 - 84	Satisfactory	Moderately Proficient
75 - 79	Fairly Satisfactory	Less Proficient
Below 75	Did Not Meet Expectation	Poor

The Table above shows that as to reading comprehension performance, the students with exposure to Japanese anime series with English subtitles were perceived to be **generally outstanding or very proficient (M=25.90)**. On this case readers use existing knowledge to make sense of text. They refer to personal experience, activate prior knowledge of the content, style, structure, as well as the strategies or learning processes they are using.

Meanwhile, the students with no exposure to anime series with English subtitles were **very satisfactory or proficient** as described by the overall mean assessment of 24.12. IN this case students were found to read fluently and can easily identify 95% of the words in a text and can read them quickly, even instantaneously.

This research result was in line with previous research conducted by Ramli, 2020 who found that video with English subtitles can improve students' reading skills and make the students more live, active, and enjoyable. According to Supangesti et., al (2018), video subtitles helped the students improve reading skills in the comprehension context.

In relation to this, Boswood (2018) also stressed that using animation brings the combination of joy and learning in the education environment that turns into the term "edutainment." In fact, he highlighted that catching students' attention is one of the most significant factors to determine success in the acquisition and learning of a second language. Thus, the use of animated films only proves that learning is motivating and enjoyable.

Moreover, Devi (2019) cited the positive benefits of using animated series in students' learning to language. According to her, use of such reduces anxiety level on students, it improves contextual comprehension with the help of subtitles displayed together with the animation, helps in the retention of concepts and not just the use of text and promotes verbal and visual literacy.

With these gained results of the study, coupled with research insights from reputable authors, it just showed that the use of video subtitles gave positive implications to the students for such affected learning improvement. The use of video subtitles in teaching and learning assisted students in understanding the text being read, in interpreting the words encountered, and in improving their vocabulary and reading comprehension performances.

Relationship Between Profile and the Vocabulary and Reading Comprehension Performances

Looking into the relationship between profile of the respondents and their vocabulary and reading performance, Table 4 presents the result of such.

Table 4. Relationship Between Profile and the Vocabulary and Reading Comprehension Performances

Profile	Performance	Genre	r	p	D	I
Age	Vocabulary	Essay	0.01	0.97	NR	NS
		Poem	-0.20	0.07	NR	NS
		Short Story	0.04	0.74	NR	NS
		All	-0.07	0.55	NR	NS
		Reading Comprehension	Essay	-0.11	0.32	NR

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Income	Vocabulary	Poem	0.01	0.91	NR	NS
		Short Story	-0.02	0.84	NR	NS
		<i>All</i>	-0.05	0.66	NR	NS
	Reading Comprehension	Essay	0.17	0.12	NR	NS
		Poem	0.24	0.03	R	S
		Short Story	0.16	0.16	NR	NS
		<i>All</i>	0.24	0.03	R	S
		Essay	0.14	0.21	NR	NS
		Poem	0.02	0.83	NR	NS
		Short Story	-0.02	0.89	NR	NS
Sex	Vocabulary	<i>All</i>	0.07	0.55	NR	NS
		Essay	0.06	0.56	NR	NS
		Poem	0.00	0.97	NR	NS
	Reading Comprehension	Short Story	0.01	0.95	NR	NS
		<i>All</i>	0.02	0.83	NR	NS
		Essay	0.09	0.42	NR	NS
		Poem	0.07	0.52	NR	NS
		Short Story	0.05	0.67	NR	NS
		<i>All</i>	0.11	0.34	NR	NS

Legend:

D - Decision *I* - Interpretation *NR* - Not Rejected
NS - Not Significant *R* - Rejected *S* - Significant

As presented in Table 4, **age does not influence the level of proficiency** of the students on vocabulary and reading comprehension in terms of essay, poem and short story. Moreover **sex**, displays that it **does not affect the students' vocabulary and reading comprehension** along with the genres of essay, poem, and short story.

However, the Table further showed that **income** earned by parents **greatly affects the vocabulary performance** of the students. Such implies that income of parents had a significant influence on the level of its vocabulary proficiency of the students.

On the other hand, as to the reading comprehension performance of the students does not influence the level of proficiency of the students.

This result further suggests that the respondents significantly differed in their vocabulary performance in its relationship to the area of income in profile.

Hence, it can be disclosed that students do vary in terms of their vocabulary and reading performances. The results of this study indicated that the relationship between the profile of respondents, such as age and sex and its vocabulary and reading performance to the genre of the literary pieces (essay, poem, short story) does not affect the performance of the students.

Yet, its income has greatly affected the students' performance in vocabulary and reading comprehension. This occurrence fits to the research conducted by Johnson, et al. (2017) which proved that children living in poverty are more likely to experience educational delays and lower academic achievement.

In addition, Naven et al. (2019) also stressed that low-income parents experience a high amount of stress, resulting in harsher disciplinary practices that can increase behavioral and cognitive issues in their children. Hence, financial instability can also result in families not being able to afford school uniforms, impacting a child's feelings of belonging.

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Comparative Analysis on the Vocabulary and Reading Comprehension Performances

Meanwhile, Table 5 presents the Comparative Analysis on the Vocabulary and Reading Performances between students who watch or have exposure to Japanese animated series with English Subtitles and those who do not watch or have no exposure to such.

Table 5. Comparative Analysis on the Vocabulary and Reading Comprehension Performances Between Students who Watch and those who Never Watch Japanese Animated Series with English Subtitles

Performance	Genre	F	p	Decision	Interpretation
Vocabulary	Essay	1.17	0.28	Not Rejected	Not Significant
	Poem	5.52	0.02	Rejected	Significant
	Short Story	3.49	0.07	Not Rejected	Not Significant
	All	5.31	0.02	Rejected	Significant
Reading Comprehension	Essay	0.01	0.91	Not Rejected	Not Significant
	Poem	9.67	0.003	Rejected	Significant
	Short Story	3.19	0.08	Not Rejected	Not Significant
	All	7.75	0.01	Rejected	Significant

The data above disclosed that in terms of vocabulary performance, the genres of essay and short story was found to be **not significant** which means it does not influence to the level of proficiency of the students between two groups.

However, in the genre of poem, **significant difference** was found in the performance between those who watch Japanese animated series with English subtitles and those who do not.

Hence, this signifies that the anime subtitled in English plays a significant role in improving instruction. It can be argued further that watching English subtitled films helps students improve their vocabulary and reading skills.

In relation to this, Furuhashi-Turner (2018) emphasized that by using materials in which students are already interested, language teachers can expect that students will enhance and improve their language competencies. Anime as a teaching tool can make the classroom more dynamic, creative, and fun making it a more learner centered learning environment that will encourage students to practice their speaking skill, besides stimulating their critical thinking skill. By adapting cartoons into the classroom teachers can promote learners' observational, analytical, and higher order thinking skills (Oliveri 2020).

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

Students who have exposure to Japanese animated films with English subtitles performed better in vocabulary and reading comprehension as compared to those who did not.

The earned income of parents impacts the learning condition of a student.

Recommendations

In the light of the conclusions drawn from the study, the following recommendations are offered:

The Administrators are encouraged to take worthwhile initiatives to support teachers' innovative learning strategies in relation to students' language proficiency, such as sending English teachers to seminars, workshops, and trainings to keep up to date on current language teaching strategies.

The English teachers are prompted to utilize Japanese animated films with English subtitles in their classes as strategy to augment the vocabulary and reading comprehension of students.

The Students are encouraged to engage themselves to view various English subtitled videos to hone their potential in vocabulary and reading skills.

The Future Researchers are stimulated to undertake similar research using other variables that are not part of the present study.

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